

Cu(I), Ag(I), Tl(I), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) Complexes of 1-Amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol

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Complexes of Cu(I), Ag(I), Tl(I), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with 1-amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol have been isolated and characterized by elemental analysis, IR and magnetic measurements. The complexes of copper, silver and thallium are polymeric in nature. Their probable structures are proposed.

1-SUBSTITUTED-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiols are versatile analytical reagents¹⁻⁴. However, no attempt has so far been made to isolate and study the structures of solid complexes of these ligands. The isolation of Cu(I), Ag(I), Tl(I), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes with 1-amino derivative of the thiol and their structural features are reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand and its metal complexes : The ligand (I) was prepared by the method of Mathes⁵. It is highly soluble in DMSO but sparingly so in alcohol. It is almost insoluble in water.

1-Amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol (I)

Ammonia (50%) was added to aqueous solutions of nitrates of Ag(I) and Tl(I) and sulphates of Cu(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) till there was a distinct smell of ammonia. NH_4Cl (2-3 g) was also added in case of Zn to avoid its hydrolysis. The clear solutions thus obtained were boiled and mixed with the hot solution of the ligand (in 1 : 1 DMSO-alcohol mixture). The metal-ligand ratio was kept slightly more than 1 : 1 in case of Ag and Tl and 1 : 2 in other cases.

The Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) complexes precipitated immediately and settled down as amorphous mass on digesting over a water bath for 1 hr. Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes separated slowly as colourless crystals. The compounds were filtered, washed with hot water, hot DMSO-water mixture (1 : 9),

ethanol and ether, and dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_{10} . Yield 75-80%.

About 1.4 g of HgCl_2 was dissolved in 100 ml ethanol and filtered. The filtrate was mixed with the ligand solution in hot 1 : 1 DMSO-ethanol mixture and heated on a water bath for 1 hr. The yellowish white complex was filtered, washed with hot water, 10% DMSO and ethanol, and dried at 110°.

Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method at 300°K. IR spectra in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Infracord spectrophotometer in KBr medium, and in the range 600-200 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating recording spectrophotometer in nujol mull.

The metal content of the complexes was estimated by the standard methods⁶ and sulphur as BaSO_4 . C, H and N were estimated microanalytically.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses (Table 1) of the complexes reveal that metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 1 in Ag(I), Cu(I), Tl(I) and Hg(II) complexes and 1 : 2 in Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes. The +1 oxidation state of copper in its metal complexes is evidenced by spin pair diamagnetic nature of the complex. It is further confirmed by the fact that 1 g atom of copper in the complex reduces 1.001 equivalent of iron.

Bonding sites of the ligand and probable structures of its complexes are elucidated by comparison of IR spectra of the metal-complexes with that of the ligand which can exist in thiol or thione form (I, a-c). IR spectrum of the ligand reveals thioamide bands (due to NCSH or HNCS group) and bands around 2500 and 750 cm^{-1} , which correspond to $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$. This confirms the existence of

tautomeric forms. In other words, the double bond in thioamide group is delocalized as shown in I(c).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH THE LIGAND 1-AMINO-4,4,6-TRIMETHYL-1H,4H-PYRIMIDINE-2-THIOL

	Analysis(%)					Colour
	C	H	S	N	Metal	
AgL	30.41 (30.23)	4.20 (4.32)	15.40 (15.11)	11.20 (11.52)	38.92 (38.0)	Yellowish white
CuL	35.70 (35.97)	5.24 (5.14)	18.10 (17.98)	13.51 (13.71)	27.40 (27.21)	White
TlL	22.68 (22.44)	3.28 (3.20)	11.11 (11.21)	8.70 (8.54)	54.16 (54.58)	Yellowish white
ZnL ₂ .H ₂ O	39.86 (39.68)	6.10 (6.14)	19.72 (19.85)	15.40 (15.12)	15.18 (15.45)	White
CdL ₂	37.0 (37.14)	5.46 (5.31)	18.20 (18.57)	14.40 (14.15)	24.60 (24.48)	White
Hg ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂	20.90 (20.68)	2.85 (2.96)	10.21 (10.34)	7.64 (7.88)	49.65 (49.40)	Yellowish white

L represents ligand. Figures within the parentheses are Calcd. values.

The ligand contains three donor sites, viz., N of amino group, N of pyrimidine ring and S of thione (thiol) group. Coordination of metal ions through N of amino group and S results in the formation of five membered ring and is probably the most favoured arrangement. The absence of a band around 2500 cm⁻¹ (due to ν_{S-H}) in the spectra of all metal complexes indicates the deprotonation of thiol group and formation of metal-sulphur bond. Appearance of new bands around 350 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes confirms the formation of this bond. Bonding of metal with S will localize the charge between N and C of thioamide group which was otherwise delocalized among N, C and S [structure I(c)]. The complexation will thus result in the shifting of ir band due to ν_{C-N} towards higher wave numbers and band due to ν_{C-S} towards lower wave numbers. Thioamide bands having major contribution from ν_{C-N} and appearing around 1300 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the ligand, shift by about 65 cm⁻¹ towards higher wave number side in the spectra of the complexes. The band around 750 cm⁻¹, which is mostly due to ν_{C-S} in the spectrum of the ligand, shifts by about 65 cm⁻¹ towards lower wave number on complexation and supports the formation of metal-sulphur bond. In case of Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) complexes, the blue shift observed in thioamide band around 1300 cm⁻¹ is, however, small (~25 cm⁻¹). This may be due to its partial compensation with the red shift, occurring due to interaction of ring N with metal atoms (which takes place as a result of polymer formation). Based on these facts, appearance of new bands around 400 cm⁻¹ (due to metal-nitrogen interaction) and known preferences of Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) complexes for tetrahedral structure⁹, the polymeric structure (II) can be proposed for the metal complexes.

(II)

The insolubility of these complexes supports the polymeric nature. However, Tl-complex is soluble in boiling water. This may be attributed to the weaker Tl-N bonds which is expected on the basis of its pronounced class 'b' behaviour⁹⁻¹¹. At higher temperature, the interaction of ring N seems to be broken resulting in a soluble monomer. IR spectral results and stoichiometry (1 : 2) indicate tetrahedral coordination⁹ of Zn(II) and Cd(II) in their complexes. Monomeric nature is also supported by the partial solubility of these complexes in water (boiling). According to elemental analyses, the Zn-complex contains water molecule. However, a band around 880 cm⁻¹, characteristic of coordinated water, is not observed in the ir spectrum of the complex. It may thus be assumed that the water molecule is lattice held.

The stoichiometry HgLCl, occurrence of ν_{Hg-Cl-Hg} (bridging) modes at 260 and 245 cm⁻¹, absence of a strong ν_{Hg-Cl} (terminal) band¹²⁻¹⁴ at 300 cm⁻¹ along with the given ir spectral results can be interpreted by the dimeric structure of mercury complex, in which Hg(II) is tetrahedrally coordinated.

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